

Electronic scientific and practical journal
**INTELLECTUALIZATION OF LOGISTICS
AND SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT**

#20 (2023)
August '23

WWW.SMART-SCM.ORG

ISSN 2708-3195

DOI.ORG/10.46783/SMART-SCM/2023-20

ISSN 2708-3195

9 772708 319005

Electronic scientific and practical publication in economic sciences

Electronic scientifically and practical journal “Intellectualization of logistics and Supply Chain Management” included in the list of scientific publications of Ukraine in the field of economic sciences (category "B"): **Order of the Ministry of Education and Culture of Ukraine dated October 10, 2022 No. 894 (Appendix 2)**

Field of science: Economic.

Specialties: 051 – Economics; 073 – Management

ISSN 2708-3195

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.46783/smart-scm/2023-20>

The electronic magazine is included in the international scientometric databases:
Index Copernicus, Google Scholar

Released 6 times a year

№ 20 (2023)

August 2023

Founder: Viold Limited Liability Company

Editor in Chief: Hryhorak M. Yu. – Doctor of Economics, Ass. Professor.

Deputy editors-in-chief: Koulyk V. A. – PhD (Economics), Professor.
Marchuk V. Ye. – Doctor of Tech. Sci., Ass. Professor.

Technical editor: Harmash O. M. – PhD (Economics), Ass. Professor.

Executive Secretary: Davidenko V. V. – PhD (Economics), Ass. Professor.

Members of the Editorial Board:

SWIEKATOWSKI Ryszard – Doctor of Economics, Professor (Poland);

POSTAN M. Ya. – Doctor of Economics, Professor;

TRUSHKINA N. V. – PhD (Economics), Corresponding Member of the Academy;

KOLOSOK V. M. – Doctor of Economics, Professor;

ILCHENKO N. B. – Doctor of Economics, Ass. Professor;

SOLOMON D. I. – Doctor of Economics, Professor (Moldova);

ALKEMA V. H. – Doctor of Economics, Professor;

Henryk DŹWIGOŁ – PhD (Economics), Professor (Poland);

SUMETS O. M. – Doctor of Economics, Ass. Professor;

STRELCOVÁ Stanislava – PhD (Economics), Ass. Professor, (Slovakia);

RISTVEJ Jozef (Mr.) PhD (Economics), Professor, (Slovakia);

ZAMIAR Zenon – Doctor of Economics, Professor, (Poland);

SMERICHEVSKA S. V. – Doctor of Economics, Professor;

GRITSENKO S. I. – Doctor of Economics, Professor;

KARPENKO O. O. – Doctor of Economics, Professor;

PATKOVSKYI S. A. – Business practitioner.

The electronic scientific and practical journal is registered in international scientometric data bases, repositories and search engines. The main characteristic of the edition is the index of scientometric data bases, which reflects the importance and effectiveness of scientific publications using indicators such as quotation index, h-index and factor impact (the number of quotations within two years after publishing).

In 2020, the International Center for Periodicals (ISSN International Center, Paris) included the Electronic Scientific and Practical Edition "Intellectualization of logistics and Supply Chain Management" in the international register of periodicals and provided it with a numerical code of international identification: ISSN 2708-3195 (Online).

Recommended for dissemination on the Internet by the Academic Council of the Department of Logistics NAU (No. 7 of February 26, 2020). Released 6 times a year. Editions references are required. The view of the editorial board does not always coincide with that of the authors.

Electronic scientifically and practical journal "Intellectualization of logistics and Supply Chain Management" included in the list of scientific publications of Ukraine in the field of economic sciences (category "B"): **Order of the Ministry of Education and Culture of Ukraine dated October 10, 2022 No. 894 (Appendix 2)**

Field of science: Economic.

Specialties: 051 – Economics; 073 – Management

t.me/smart_scm
facebook.com/Smart.SCM.org
twitter.com/ScmSmart

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.46783/smart-scm/2023-20>
e-mail: support@smart-scm.org

тел.: (063) 593-30-41
<https://smart-scm.org>

Contents

INTRODUCTION	5
MARCHENKO V. S. Graduate of the National Aviation University (Ukraine), BUGAYKO D.O. Doctor of Science (Economics), Professor (Associate), Corresponding Member of the Academy of Economic Sciences of Ukraine, Vice - Director of ES International Cooperation and Education Institute, Instructor of ICAO Institute, Professor of the Logistics Department National Aviation University (Ukraine), BUGAYKO D.D. Student of the Logistics Department National Aviation University (Ukraine)	
SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF A LOGISTICS COMPANY BASED ON THE IMPLEMENTATION OF A «GREEN» BUSINESS STRATEGY	6 – 18
REZNIK V.V. Postgraduate Student, National Aviation University (Ukraine), BUGAYKO D.O. Doctor of Science (Economics), Professor (Associate), Corresponding Member of the Academy of Economic Sciences of Ukraine, Vice - Director of ES International Cooperation and Education Institute, Instructor of ICAO Institute, Professor of the Logistics Department National Aviation University (Ukraine)	
<i>COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE LEGISLATION OF UKRAINE AND INTERNATIONAL NORMS THAT REGULATE THE IMPLEMENTATION AND FORMATION OF AVIATION LOGISTICS SYSTEM</i>	19 – 30
GURINA G.S. Doctor of Economics, Professor, Professor of department of management of foreign economic activity of enterprises of National Aviation University (Ukraine), PODRIEZA S.M. Doctor of Economics, Professor, Professor of department of management of foreign economic activity of enterprises of National Aviation University (Ukraine), BUT V.A. Candidate of Public Administration National Aviation University (Ukraine)	
<i>ENVIRONMENTAL TRENDS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF AVIATION MANAGEMENT</i>	31 – 37
KYRYLENKO O.M. Doctor of Economics, Professor, Head of the Department of Foreign Economic Activity of Enterprises of National Aviation University (Ukraine), NOVAK V.O. PhD (Economics), Professor, Professor of the Department of Foreign Economic Activity Management of National Aviation University (Ukraine), PODRIEZA M.S. Graduate student of the Department of Management foreign economic activity of enterprises of National Aviation University (Ukraine)	
<i>KEY ASPECTS OF CORPORATE RESPONSIBILITY OF AVIATION ENTERPRISES</i>	38 – 45
GRYTSENKO S.I. Doctor of Economics, Professor, Professor of Logistics Department of National Aviation University), NINICH V.Z master student of Logistics Department of National Aviation University (Ukraine)	
<i>CLUSTERING OF LOGISTICS SUPPLY CHAINS IN THE PROCESS OF UKRAINE'S EUROINTEGRATION</i>	46 – 57
ZAHORODNIA A.S. Postgraduate of Department of Management named after Professor Yosyp S. Zavadsky, National university of life and environmental science of Ukraine (Ukraine)	
<i>FORMATION OF THE ECONOMIC SECURITY MANAGEMENT STRATEGY OF THE ENTERPRISE</i>	58 – 64

UDC 656.7.086

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.46783/smart-scm/2023-20-4>

JEL Classification: L82, M15

Received: 15 August 2023

Kyrylenko O.M. Doctor of Economics, Professor, Head of the Department of Foreign Economic Activity of Enterprises of National Aviation University (Ukraine)

ORCID – 0000-0003-2406-7050

Researcher ID –

Scopus author id: –

Novak V.O. PhD (Economics), Professor, Professor of the Department of Foreign Economic Activity Management of National Aviation University (Ukraine)

ORCID – 0000-0001-6899-2016

Researcher ID –

Scopus author id: –

Podrieza M.S. Graduate student of the Department of Management foreign economic activity of enterprises of National Aviation University (Ukraine)

ORCID –

Researcher ID –

Scopus author id: –

KEY ASPECTS OF CORPORATE RESPONSIBILITY OF AVIATION ENTERPRISES

Oksana Kyrylenko, Valentyna Novak, Mykhailo Podrieza. "Key aspects of corporate responsibility of aviation enterprises". *This scientific article is devoted to the study of corporate responsibility of aviation enterprises and their impact on the general social space. The growing attention to environmental issues puts the reputation of aviation companies at risk and forces them to improve their corporate responsibility. This article proposes to analyze various aspects of corporate responsibility of aviation enterprises and considers prospects for their further development. In conditions of increased awareness of investors and financial institutions, the latter prefer more sustainable business from the point of view of financial, social and economic indicators. In this regard, the importance of intangible factors of economic growth of the enterprise, such as the development of labor potential, promotion of employment, compliance with social protection standards and human rights, implementation of environmental aspects of activity, is increasing. In such conditions, the analysis of the company's social policy, which is implemented by the mechanism of corporate social responsibility, becomes relevant. Under modern conditions of increasing global instability, enterprises are interested in increasing the level of predictability of the process of social and economic development, the institutional environment, the achievement of political and economic stability from local to global levels, the sustainable development of social and labor relations, the absence of social conflicts and economic crises, which is necessary for effective activity. Therefore, the formation of a strategy of corporate social responsibility in the*

practice of domestic enterprises at the level of modern business entities is of great importance, which will ensure their sustainable development.

Keywords: corporate social responsibility, aviation enterprises, business sustainability, airline reputation, leadership and innovation in business.

Оксана Кириленко, Валентина Новак, Михайло Подреза. *«Ключові аспекти корпоративної відповідальності авіаційних підприємств».* Ця наукова стаття присвячена дослідженню корпоративної відповідальності авіаційних підприємств і їхнього впливу на загальний соціальний простір. Зростаюча увага до екологічних проблем ставить під загрозу репутацію авіаційних компаній та змушує їх вдосконалювати свою корпоративну відповідальність. Ця стаття пропонує аналізувати різні аспекти корпоративної відповідальності авіаційних підприємств та розглядає перспективи для їхнього подальшого розвитку. В умовах підвищення рівня інформованості інвесторів та фінансових інститутів, останні надають перевагу більш стійкому бізнесу з точки зору фінансових, соціальних та економічних показників. У зв'язку з цим зростає значущість нематеріальних чинників економічного зростання підприємства, таких як розвиток трудового потенціалу, сприяння зайнятості, дотримання стандартів соціального захисту та прав людини, реалізація екологічних аспектів діяльності. У таких умовах актуальності набуває аналіз соціальної політики підприємства, що реалізується механізмом корпоративної соціальної відповідальності. За сучасних умов підвищення глобальної нестабільності підприємства зацікавлені у збільшенні рівня передбачуваності процесу розвитку суспільства та економіки, інституційного середовища, досягнення політичної та економічної стабільності від локального до глобального рівнів, стійкого розвитку соціально-трудова відносин, відсутності соціальних конфліктів та економічних криз, що необхідно для ефективної діяльності. Тому великого значення набуває формування на рівні сучасних суб'єктів господарювання стратегії корпоративної соціальної відповідальності у практиці вітчизняних підприємств, що забезпечуватиме їх сталий розвиток.

Ключові слова: корпоративна соціальна відповідальність, авіаційні підприємства, стійкість бізнесу, репутація авіапідприємств, лідерство та інновації в бізнесі

Introduction. In today's world, aviation plays an important role in the global economy and provides efficient transportation of passengers and cargo. However, along with their advantages, aviation enterprises also face challenges related to the preservation of the environment. That is why there is a need to consider the corporate responsibility of aviation companies. For the development of civilized social relations, it is important to form a parity of interests of the main participants in economic relations - state and local authorities, corporate structures, public organizations, and citizens. The mechanism of social responsibility acts as an important tool for building partnerships between these subjects when solving urgent issues.

Presentation of the main results. The reasons for the growing interest in the

corporate responsibility of aviation enterprises are revealed by the following theses. Growing awareness of climate change and the challenges of environmental pollution is putting the reputation of airline companies at risk. Consumers, investors and other stakeholders are becoming more and more aware and demanding regarding the environmental performance of enterprises. Therefore, aviation companies are forced to pay attention to their corporate responsibility. And top management should pay attention to the following aspects:

– modern international and national paradigms of forming norms of business ethics and leadership in society, cross-cultural and international aspects of business ethics and leadership;

– honesty, transparency, standards, trust, reputation, fairness and ethics in business, trade, management, marketing, public communications, finance, public administration and international economic relations;

– leadership and innovation in business, trade, management, marketing, public communications, finance, public administration and international economic relations in different countries [3];

– corporate social responsibility and social entrepreneurship;

– introduction of ethical standards and modern democratic practices in socio-economic processes to ensure social justice, gender and social equality, protection of corporate and personal rights and freedoms throughout the world;

– behavioral economics, coordination of stakeholders' interests, public-private and intersectoral business partnership;

– effective and ethical business communications and public relations, social and ethical marketing;

– professional ethics and standards of financial institutions and regulators; trust and reputation in financial relations; behavioral finance; non-financial corporate reporting; transparency of finances, accounting and taxation; international experience and standards for preventing unethical, unscrupulous and non-transparent financial relations;

– human capital management, management, psychology of leadership, organizational culture, motivation, professional ethics;

– client-oriented business management, quality of services, protection of consumer interests in different countries.

Environmental responsibility. The aviation industry has a significant impact on climate change and the environment through greenhouse gas emissions, noise pollution and the use of natural resources. The corporate responsibility of aviation enterprises includes efforts to minimize the

impact on the environment through the introduction of new technologies, the use of biofuels, rational consumption of resources and other measures.[1]

Social responsibility. Aviation enterprises must also take into account the social aspects of their activities. This includes ensuring the safety and comfort of passengers, creating jobs, ensuring equal opportunities and promoting the development of local communities.

Economic responsibility. Corporate responsibility of aviation enterprises also covers economic sustainability. Enterprises must act in accordance with economic principles, ensure financial stability, effective management of resources and promote economic development.

The prospects for the development of corporate responsibility of aviation enterprises are in the following positions. Innovative technologies. One of the key directions in the development of corporate responsibility of aviation enterprises is the introduction of new technologies aimed at reducing the negative impact on the environment. For example, the development and use of environmentally friendly fuels, smart energy efficiency management systems and efficient use of resources can help aviation companies reduce their environmental footprints.

Cooperation with interested parties. Aviation enterprises have to interact more and more with stakeholders, such as government bodies, public organizations, scientific institutions and consumers [4]. This will facilitate the exchange of information, joint projects and implementation of best practices in the field of corporate responsibility. Cooperation may include joint initiatives to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, use renewable energy sources, and improve working conditions. Social responsibility, regardless of the level and scale of research, is defined at the global, national, regional and industrial levels. The global level reveals the content of social responsibility by identifying the problems and conditions of

existence of humanity and finding ways to solve them through the spread of social integration aimed at ensuring sustainable development regardless of place of residence and racial affiliation. The question of the expediency of introducing the principles of social responsibility into the business practice of domestic enterprises should not cause doubt. However, at present, a purely declarative approach to this issue prevails in the Ukrainian business environment. Although most companies declare themselves to be socially responsible, clear and systematic work in this direction is carried out by units. Social responsibility is one of those factors that affects the overall economic efficiency of enterprises. However, this is achieved only under the condition of constant activity in the field of corporate social responsibility. Awareness of this fact will undoubtedly lead to increased attention of business units to issues that reflect work towards increasing the overall level of response to the demands of stakeholders (interested persons). Social responsibility of business in Ukraine is developing spontaneously. There are no clearly written state or balanced corporate decisions for its implementation, in most cases those directions of business socialization that can ensure maximum return are not defined [6]. Social responsibility arises as an objective need not only of society, but also of enterprises themselves, which strive to find their place in a competitive environment, their consumers, to interest national and foreign partners, highly qualified specialists in cooperation.

Implementation of standards and certification. Standards and certification systems aimed at defining and measuring the corporate responsibility of aviation enterprises are an important tool for promoting the development of this industry. The implementation of such standards, for example, the International Reporting Standard GRI (Global Reporting Initiative) or ISO 14001 standards (environmental management systems), will allow aviation

companies to more systematically define their goals and results in the field of corporate responsibility.

Ethical practices and transparency. Ethical practices, such as setting high safety and quality standards, displaying information about environmental impact and social initiatives in reports and communications, play an important role in building the trust of consumers and other stakeholders. Transparency and openness about one's actions and efforts is an important step in ensuring corporate responsibility.

Corporate responsibility of aviation enterprises is of great importance in the context of sustainable development and environmental protection. Growing attention to environmental issues, changing consumer demands and a strengthening regulatory environment are challenging businesses to step up their corporate responsibility efforts. Implementation of innovative technologies, cooperation with interested parties, use of standards and certification, as well as ethical practices and transparency are key directions for further development of this field.

Aviation corporate responsibility research should continue to identify best practices, develop new strategies, and raise awareness of business ethics.

The role of government bodies and regulation. Government bodies have an important role in regulating the corporate responsibility of aviation enterprises. By establishing strict regulatory requirements, creating an environmentally oriented regulatory framework and providing financial incentives, governments can promote the growth of corporate responsibility in the aviation industry. It is also important that governments promote research and development aimed at improving the environmental performance of aviation technology.

Challenges and obstacles. Despite the growing interest in aviation corporate responsibility, there are some challenges and obstacles that need to be considered. These include the high costs of implementing new

technologies and green initiatives, technological limitations, the instability of market conditions, and the lack of uniform standards and methodologies for measuring environmental impact. To overcome these obstacles, it is necessary to promote innovation, investment in research and development of technology, as well as to promote cooperation and exchange of best practices between aviation companies.

Impact on business and public perception. Improving the corporate responsibility of aviation companies can have a significant impact on their business performance and public perception. Companies that pay attention to environmental and social responsibility can have an advantage over competitors, gain the support of consumers and investors, and preserve their reputation in the event of environmental incidents or scandalous situations. However, it must be noted that corporate responsibility must be honest and convincing, not just a marketing tool. [2]

Corporate responsibility of aviation enterprises is an important factor for ensuring the sustainable development of the industry and preservation of the environment. The growing attention to environmental problems and the demands of stakeholders put companies in front of the need to change and actively work to reduce their negative impact. Innovative technologies, collaboration with stakeholders, the use of standards and certifications, as well as ethical practices and transparency are key factors in achieving corporate responsibility goals. It is important that airlines continue to work hard to improve their practices and ensure that they strike the right balance between the social, environmental and economic aspects of their operations.

After the end of the war, Ukraine must face the challenge of restoring its aviation potential, which could have been damaged during the armed conflict. Ukraine's aviation industry has always been important to the country, and after the war it has great

potential for development and is a key element of economic revival.

One of the main tasks is the restructuring of aviation enterprises and their return to full activity. This may require investment and governance reform. In addition, the preservation and attraction of highly qualified specialists in the industry is an important factor for the successful revival of aviation.

Aircraft development and modernization of existing aircraft can also provide a positive market impact. Ukraine has rich experience in aircraft construction and development of aviation equipment, and focusing efforts in this field can help to become competitive in the international market.[4]

In addition, an important step is to ensure the safety of the aviation space. The end of the war may lead to the need to review and update safety norms and standards, which will help avoid incidents and ensure passenger comfort and trust in Ukrainian aviation.

To a large extent, the development of the aviation sector will be facilitated by the stimulation of tourist traffic to Ukraine. Creating new routes and increasing the frequency of flights to popular tourist destinations will help attract foreign tourists and support domestic tourism.

In addition to internal efforts, it is also important to establish partnerships with international airlines and resume international flights. This will help integrate the Ukrainian aviation market into the global system and increase its competitiveness.

Overall, reviving Ukraine's aviation potential after the end of the war will require a concerted effort by government, business and other stakeholders. This is possible thanks to responsible planning, investment in technology and human resource development. I am sure that with appropriate efforts, Ukraine will be able to return to the international arena as a strong player in the field of aviation.

One of the key factors in restoring Ukraine's aviation potential is the attraction of foreign investments. Foreign investment can

be used to modernize existing aviation infrastructure, purchase new equipment and aircraft, and improve technological processes in the industry. The government should create a favorable investment climate and ensure transparency in regulation, which will help attract foreign companies and support their participation in the development of Ukrainian aviation.

Development of regional aviation. In addition to stimulating international tourism, the development of regional aviation also has great potential for supporting the socio-economic development of Ukraine's regions. The launch of regular flights between cities and regions will help reduce the remoteness of territories, improve the availability of medical and educational services, attract investments and ensure the growth of regional economies. The government can promote the development of regional aviation by providing financial support, incentivizing investors and providing advantages for airlines operating flights to less developed regions.

Training and development of personnel. One of the important aspects of the successful development of the aviation industry is the provision of adequate training and development of personnel. Continuous training of pilots, aviation technicians, air traffic controllers and other personnel will help ensure the safety of air travel and the efficient functioning of the aviation sector. In addition, it is necessary to stimulate young people to choose professions in aviation, in particular, by creating favorable conditions for training and providing prospects for career development.

Environmental sustainability. The increase in aviation potential should be accompanied by paying attention to the environmental aspect. Reducing emissions of harmful substances into the air, efficient use of fuel and the development of biofuels can contribute to reducing the negative impact of aviation on the environment. The government can support scientific research in the field of environmental sustainability of

aviation, as well as provide benefits and support to airlines that actively implement environmentally friendly technologies.

International cooperation. Ensuring the effective development of the aviation potential also requires international cooperation. The Government of Ukraine should actively interact with international aviation organizations and other states in order to jointly solve problems, create a favorable international legal field for air transportation, and attract external expertise and support.[8]

Conclusions. After the end of the war, Ukraine will face great challenges in restoring its aviation potential. Investments in the modernization and development of infrastructure, stimulation of regional aviation, training and development of personnel, environmental sustainability and international cooperation are key factors for the successful development of the aviation sector. With appropriate efforts by government, business and other stakeholders, Ukraine can revive its aviation industry and return to the world stage as a strong aviation player. The development of corporate social responsibility at Ukrainian enterprises is possible only if there are interests of society, the state and other stakeholders. This becomes an important moment for the promotion of this concept not only on a global scale, but also in Ukraine as a whole. This can be used to prove the relevance of implementing the concept of corporate social responsibility in the system of strategic development of enterprises. The creation of corporate social responsible government and business is directly related to the implementation of the concept of sustainable development. Corporate social responsibility of business is a subsystem of corporate social responsibility of the general system of social interaction, as well as a means of guaranteeing and protecting social relations, which are established by certain subjects and guaranteed by certain means in order to respect human rights, is a manifestation of the culture of society, the

realization of its public interests and regulated by social norms, controlled by sanctions. This phenomenon represents the elements of the superstructure of society, which depend on the level of development of economic, political and social relations; develops and transforms together with social relations; is a voluntary initiative of organizations (companies) to comply with ethical norms in the field of social interaction and to assume responsibility for the impact on the environment, partners, consumers, employees and communities. World practice shows that the concept of socially responsible business is successfully developing and is in the process of constant changes and improvements. The study made it possible to conclude that the mechanisms of the system of corporate social responsibility have not yet received appropriate distribution at domestic enterprises. Statistics show that only every third company owner in our country knows

about the term and concept of corporate social responsibility, and standards and rules for Ukrainian business have not yet been created. The principles of corporate social responsibility reveal the main provisions that show the enterprise in its entirety, its essence and work activity as a whole and whether it is related to the implementation of corporate social responsibility. If you do not observe at least one of the principles of corporate social responsibility, which are created at the expense of public expectations, then its essence is falsified. The conducted research showed that the Ukrainian economic system has not yet passed all the necessary stages of development and formation, which abroad have already shown the importance of corporate social responsibility and the results of its work as a whole. There are still a large number of problems within our country that hinder implementation processes in the field of corporate social responsibility.

References

1. Brecharia S. G. Stages of the formation of corporate and social responsibility of Ukrainian business [Electronic resource] - 2018. - Resource access mode: https://ipiend.gov.ua/wp-content/uploads/2018/07/brecharia_etapy.pdf
2. Bocharova N. A. Environmental aspect of corporate social responsibility of enterprises - 2020. - No. 35. – P. 34–43.
3. Information on the UN Global Compact [Electronic resource] - Access to the resource <https://globalcompact.org.ua/pro-nas/gd-oon-v-ukraini/>
4. Classification of forms and types of corporate social responsibility [Electronic resource] - Resource access mode https://pidru4niki.com/91751/sotsiologiya/klasifikatsiya_form_vidiv_sotsialnoyi_vidpovidalnosti
5. Mazurenko V. P. Modern concept of corporate social responsibility in international business [Electronic resource] – Access to the resource: <http://www.economy.nayka.com.ua/?op=1&z=1199>.
6. Mints O. Yu. Implementation of international standards in the field of corporate social responsibility at industrial enterprises of Ukraine [Electronic resource] - 2019. - Access to the resource: http://www.economy.nayka.com.ua/pdf/9_2019/7.pdf
7. Hurina G.S. Implementation of the concept of public-private partnership as a key to the development and competitiveness of the export potential of the country's aviation complex. IV International Conference "Science and Modernity: Challenges of Globalization". Kyiv. Center for scientific publications. pp. 26-29. 2018.

8. Gurina G.S., Podrieza S.M. (2023) "Globalization challenges of strategic management of the export potential of aviation complex enterprises". – Intellectualization of logistics and Supply Chain Management. [Online], vol.19, pp.19-23, available at: <https://smart-scm.org/en/journal-19-2023/globalization-challenges-of-strategic-management-of-the-export-potential-of-aviation-complex-enterprises/>. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.46783/smart-scm/2023-19-23>

9. Kyrylenko O.M., Novak V.O., Podrieza M.S. (2023) "The place of organizational culture in the management system of aviation enterprises". – Intellectualization of logistics and Supply Chain Management. [Online], vol.19, pp.45-50, available at: <https://smart-scm.org/en/journal-19-2023/the-place-of-organizational-culture-in-the-management-system-of-aviation-enterprises/>. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.46783/smart-scm/2023-19-4>